

magnetically for 1.5 h. Then ice was added to decompose excess of LiAlH_4 and the ether layer was washed with sodium tartarate solution (50 ml). Ether on evaporation gave solid which when recrystallised from alcohol gave **4** (12 g, 51%), m.p. 75° (Found: C, 81.75; H, 7.86; N, 10.01). $\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{22}\text{N}_2$ requires: C, 81.01; H, 7.91; N, 10.07%; ν_{max} (nujol) 3300 (NH_2), 1600 ($\text{C}=\text{C}$) and 1500 cm^{-1} ($\text{C}-\text{N}$); δ (TFA) 1.0 (2H, m, CH_2), 2.1 (3H, s, ArCH_3), 2.15 (3H, s, C_2-CH_3), 2.6 (2H, t, CH_2NH_2), 3.7 (2H, t, NCH_2), 4.2 (2H, s, NH) and 7.05–7.7 (8H, m, ArH); M^+ , 278 (0.2%), 187 (50%), 160 (25%), 120 (100%), 105 (15%), 91 (33%), 77 (17%) and 65 (10%).

Compounds **4b**, **4e**, **4g**, **4h** and **4i** (Table 1) were prepared according to general method used for the preparation of **4c**.

N-(N-Phenylcarbonylamino propyl)-2,5-dimethyl-3-phenylindole (4c): A mixture of **4** (0.139 g; 0.0005 mol) and phenylisocyanate (0.0595 g, 0.0005 mol) in THF (10 ml) was refluxed on a water-bath for ~5 h, then cooled and the solvent was removed under reduced pressure. The solid formed was recrystallised from ethanol to give **4c** (0.158 g, 80%), m.p. 175° (Found: C, 78.53; H, 6.75; N, 10.55). $\text{C}_{28}\text{H}_{27}\text{N}_3\text{O}$ requires: C, 78.58; H, 6.80; N, 10.57%.

The following experimental procedure forms a general method for the preparation of **4a**, **4d** and **4f**.

N-(N-4-Hydroxybenzylideneamino propyl)-2,5-dimethyl-3-phenylindole (4f): A mixture of **4** (0.139 g, 0.0005 mol) and *p*-hydroxybenzaldehyde (0.062 g, 0.0005 mol) in methanol (10 ml) was refluxed for ~6 h, and the solvent was then removed under reduced pressure. The solid obtained which when recrystallised from ethanol to give **4f** (0.131 g, 69%), m.p. 105° (Found: C, 81.60; H, 6.75; N, 7.30). $\text{C}_{26}\text{H}_{26}\text{N}_2\text{O}$ requires: C, 81.76; H, 6.80; N, 7.32%.

Acknowledgement

The authors thank U.G.C., New Delhi, for awarding a Teacher Fellowship to one of them (D.S.K.).

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Synthesis of 2-(2'-Methoxyanilino)-4-(benzamido-2'-yloxy)-6-(substituted-phenylureido)-s-triazine Derivatives and Study of their Antibacterial Activity

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Manuscript received 16 April 1987, accepted 3 November 1987

UREA derivatives possess wide therapeutic activities, such as antibacterial¹, antithyroid, hypnotic and anaesthetic, hypoglycemic², anthelmintic, diuretic³ and biocidal. Phenylacetamidourea derivatives are active anticonvulsants. Salicylamide has been claimed to be more potent than aspirin. Salicylamide has a marked anthelmintic, antispasmodic, antipyretic and sedative action^{4,5}.

To study the antibacterial⁶ activity of compounds of the type **1** were synthesised by the condensation of cyanuric chloride (0.1 M) and *o*-anisidine (0.1 M). The resulted product was afforded to react with salicylamide in equimolecular proportion. The compound obtained was made to condense with various phenyl ureas to get the compounds of the type **1**.

Experimental

2-(2'-Methoxyanilino)-4,6-dichloro-s-triazine: *o*-Anisidine (0.01 mol) dissolved in acetone was added to a well stirred solution of cyanuric chloride (0.01 mol) dissolved in acetone at $0-5^\circ$. pH of the solution was maintained 7 by adding aqueous 2% NaOH during the reaction. The reaction mixture was stirred for 2 h. Crushed ice was then added to it and filtered, and the resulting solid was crystallised from ethanol, (86%), m.p. 126° .

2-(2'-Methoxyanilino)-4-(benzamido-2'-yloxy)-6-chloro-s-triazine: Salicylamide (0.01 mol) was dissolved in acetone and 5% NaOH solution was added dropwise during 1.5 h to a mechanically stirred solution of 2-(2'-methoxyanilino)-4,6-dichloro-s-triazine (0.01 mol) in dioxane at 35° . The temperature was gradually increased to 45° during 2 h. pH was maintained by addition of aqueous NaOH. The reaction mixture was cooled to room temperature. It was added in crushed ice and HCl solution (2%). The compound obtained was filtered, dried and recrystallised from benzene, (76%), m.p. 162° .

General method for preparation of 2-(2'-methoxyanilino)-4-(benzamido-2'-yloxy)-6-(phenylureido)-s-

triazine: 2-(2'-Methoxyanilino)-4-(benzamido-2'-yl-oxo)-6-chloro-*s*-triazine (0.01 mol) and various phenylureas (0.01 mol) in acetone or dioxane were refluxed for 3 h on a water-bath keeping pH of the solution at 7 by adding aqueous 2% NaOH. The resulting clear solution was added in crushed ice, filtered and recrystallised from ethanol. The yield of the compounds varied from 69 to 82%, m.p. R = phenyl, 167°; *o*-tolyl, 156°; *m*-tolyl, 172°; *p*-tolyl, 180°; *o*-nitrophenyl 169°; *m* nitrophenyl 186°; *p*-nitrophenyl, 154°; *o*-chlorophenyl, 135°; *m*-chlorophenyl, 128°; *p*-chlorophenyl, 140°.

Ir spectra (KBr) recorded on a Parkin-Elmer spectrophotometer revealed the following bands for all compounds in general: 1540-1510 (NH bend), 1660-1600 (C-O stretch), 1240-1200 (C-O-C stretch) and 870-850 cm^{-1} (C_6N_3 stretch).

Antibacterial activity: The purified product was screened for antibacterial activity by cup-plate method using a species of gram-positive bacteria (*S. aureus*) and a species of gram-negative bacteria (*E. coli*). Testing was carried out in ethanol solution at a concentration of 10 mg ml^{-1} . The zone of inhibition of the test solutions were recorded.

The zone of inhibition was found considerable against *S. aureus*, for 2-(2'-methoxyanilino)-4-(benzamido-2'-yl-oxo)-6-(phenylureido)-*s*-triazine and 2-(2'-methoxyanilino)-4-(benzamido-2'-yl-oxo)-6-(3'-methylphenylureido)-*s*-triazine as 2.5 and 2.0 mm, respectively. While the marked zone of inhibition was obtained against *E. coli*, for 2-(2'-methoxyanilino)-4-(benzamido-2'-yl-oxo)-6-(3'-methylphenylureido)-*s*-triazine and 2-(2'-methoxyanilino)-4-(benzamido-2'-yl-oxo)-6-(2'-nitrophenylureido)-*s*-triazine as 2.0 and 1.0 mm, respectively.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to South Gujarat University for facilities. The authors are also thankful to Atic Industries, for ir spectra.

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Olean-12-ene-28-oic-3-O- β -D-glucopyranosyl-(1 \rightarrow 4)-O- α -L-xylopyranoside from *Gardenia latifolia* Ait. Stems

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Manuscript received 10 February 1987, revised 17 September 1987, accepted 30 October 1987

GARDENIA latifolia (Ait.)¹ N.O. Rubiaceae is known as 'Papra' in Hindi and found throughout the greater parts of India. Earlier workers have already reported the presence of episiaeresinolic acid and D-mannitol, sitosterol, oleanolic acid, siarsinolic, spinosis acid and hederagenin from the bark and stem bark respectively^{2,3}.

The methanol soluble part of the rectified spirit extract of the stem yielded a saponin, which was found to be homogeneous on tlc and analysed for $\text{C}_{41}\text{H}_{66}\text{O}_{13}$, m.p. 218°, $[\alpha]_D^{25} - 16.8^\circ$ (in pyridine), $M^+ 750$. It responded to all the characteristic reactions of saponin⁴⁻⁶. On acid hydrolysis it yielded sapogenin and sugars identified as D-glucose and L-xylose (by co-pc and tlc). The sapogenin analysed for $\text{C}_{30}\text{H}_{48}\text{O}_8$, m.p. 307° $[\alpha]_D^{25} + 78.5^\circ$ (in CHCl_3), $M^+ 456$. It gave all the colour reactions characteristic of pentacyclic triterpene. It formed a monoacetyl derivative ($\text{C}_{32}\text{H}_{48}\text{O}_4$, m.p. 269°) with Ac_2O /pyridine, confirming the presence of one OH group. It was identified as oleanolic acid by co-pc, tlc and m.m.p.; ν_{max} (KBr) 3420, 3030, 2900, 1667, 1391, 1381, 1370, 1360, 1346, 1295, 810 and 800 cm^{-1} ; δ 0.95, 0.97, 0.82, 0.89, 1.10, 1.26-2.00, 2.03, 3.2, 5.50, 2.50, 4.29, 5.47, 3.40-4.18, 2.06, 2.08, 2.00, 2.15, 2.18 and 2.22; m/e 415, 441, 411, 410, 395, 248, 207, 203, 189, 175 and 133. Positive Zimmermann test while indicated the presence of C_8 -OH. On partial hydrolysis with 0.02 N H_2SO_4 it showed the appearance of D-glucose first followed by L-xylose thereby showing D-glucose to be terminal sugar.

The saponin on permethylation by Kuhn⁸ procedure yielded 2,3 di-O-methylxylose and 2,3,4,6-tetra-O-methyl-D-glucose. Periodate⁹ oxidation and per-methylation followed by hydrolysis confirmed that both the sugars were present in pyranose form. Enzymatic¹⁰ hydrolysis with enzyme emulsion revealed β -linkage between L-xylose and D glucose and α -linkage between sapogenin and L-xylose. Specific rotation measurements confirmed that glucose was present in D-form and xylose in L-form. Thus the structure of the saponin was assigned as olean-12-ene-28-oic-3-O-D-glucopyranosyl (1 \rightarrow 4)-O- α -L-xylopyranoside.

Experimental

The stem (2 kg) of *Gardenia latifolia* (Ait.) collected locally and authenticated by the Botany Department of this University, was air-dried